

Wine and its components' analysis

Dr Mark Christopher Arokiaraj,
36 Montorsier street,
Pondicherry, India.
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Abstract

Wine has been known for its beneficial aspects since ancient years. Cardiovascular benefits are known,^{1,2} but the exact mechanism has yet to be deciphered. The multifarious benefits warrant a deeper level of analysis. The study was performed for the possible understanding of the mechanisms of wine's benefits. The known components of wine were taken, and it was analysed for the resultant molecule after interaction with the original ingredients using IBM RXN. The resultant forward prediction molecule was tested for pharmacokinetic properties. Thereafter, the possible drug target was analysed using PLATO prediction. The results show a prominent interaction with Escherichia coli adhesion fimbriae protein. When the components of bread was added (amylopectin and maltose) to the equation of the components of wine, the result simplifies to quercetin by IBM RXN, though the confidence is low. By PLATO prediction, quercetin has a reliable targets on Escherichia coli. This shows a possible benefit in the treatment and prevention of Escherichia coli infections, which is the commonest organism in urinary tract infections. The results are theoretical and preliminary, and they need to be evaluated in real-time retrospective patient models. There are possibilities for therapeutic doses of wine in prevention and treatment of complicated urinary tract infections.

Component analysis

The components of wine were analysed.

Ethanol + sulphites + resveratrol + quercetin – the analysis was made through IBM RXN and the resultant compound was obtained with the smiles below.

The model of forward prediction had a confidence of 0.54.

Table 1 shows the component analysis by IBM RXN.

The resultant molecule was analysed for physicochemical properties.

The table below summarises the properties which shows high water solubility and low GI score. There are possibilities for synthetic ability. Target fishing analysis through PLATO prediction showed an high score (4.5) for the adhesin protein of E coli’s fimbriae.

Table 2 shows the physicochemical properties through Swiss ADME.

When the components of bread was added (amylopectin and maltose) to the equation of the components of wine, the result of the equation simplifies to quercetin. The confidence of this equation is low - 0.21. Some of the specific targets by PLATO³ fishing prediction were Beta-lactamase AmpC: Escherichia coli K-12 and Enoyl-[acyl-carrier-protein] reductase: Escherichia coli K-12 with a high reliability factor – 13, as shown in the supplement (Plato quercetin supplement).

Conclusion: The results are theoretical and preliminary, and they need to be evaluated in real-time retrospective patient models. There are possibilities for therapeutic doses of wine in prevention and treatment of complicated urinary tract infections.

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